

Pollen Category – CANOPY TREES	Reference Image(s)	Observed Image(s)	
<p>“a” – Acer type <i>A. saccharum</i> <i>A. saccharinum</i> <i>A. rubrum</i></p>			
	<p>“p” – Populus type <i>P. deltoides</i> <i>P. tremuloides</i> <i>P. sp.</i></p>	<p style="text-align: right;">*ZOOM</p>	

Pollen Category – CANOPY TREES	Reference Image(s)	Observed Image(s)
<p>“b” – Betulaceae type <i>Betula sp.</i> <i>Ostrya sp.</i> <i>Carpinus sp.</i></p>	<p><i>Betula</i></p>	
<p>“c” – Carya type <i>C. ovata</i> <i>C. cordiformis</i> <i>C. sp.</i></p>		
<p>“e” – Fagus type <i>F. sylvatica</i> <i>F. grandifolia</i></p>		

Pollen Category – CANOPY TREES	Reference Image(s)	Observed Image(s)
<p>“j”– Juglans type <i>J. nigra</i></p>		
<p>“v” – Pine type <i>Pinus sp.</i> <i>Picea sp.</i> <i>Abies sp.</i></p>	<p><i>no reference slide collected</i></p>	<p>KRU4341, <i>Andrena carlini</i>, 5/21/2019</p>

Pollen Category – CANOPY TREES	Reference Image(s)	Observed Image(s)
<p>“q” – Quercus type</p> <p><i>Q. alba</i> <i>Q. rubra</i> <i>Q. velutina</i> <i>Q. sp.</i></p>		
<p>“x” – Fraxinus type</p> <p><i>F. americana</i> <i>F. pensylvanica</i></p>		

Pollen Category – NON-CANOPY TREES/SHRUBS	Reference Image(s)	Observed Image(s)
<p>“w” – Salix type <i>S. sp.</i></p>		
<p>“z” – Lonicera type <i>L. sp.</i></p>		

Pollen Category – NON-CANOPY TREES/SHRUBS	Reference Image(s)	Observed Image(s)
<p>“8” – Ericaeeae type</p>	<p><i>no reference slide collected</i></p>	<p>KRU4747, <i>Lasioglossum hitchensi</i>, 5/28/2019</p>
<p>“2” – Rhus type <i>R. typhina</i> <i>R. sp.</i></p>	<p><i>no reference slide collected</i></p>	<p>?????</p>

Pollen Category – ROSACEAE	Reference Image(s)	Observed Image(s)
<p>“r” – Rosaceae apple type</p> <p><i>Malus sp.</i> <i>Pyrus sp.</i> <i>Prunus sp.</i> <i>Rubus sp.</i> <i>Amelanchier sp.</i></p>	<p><i>Malus sp.</i></p>	
<p>“f” – Rosaceae strawberry type</p> <p><i>F. vesca</i> <i>F. sp.</i></p>		

Pollen Category – HERBACEOUS	Reference Image(s)	Observed Image(s)
<p>“i” – Brassica type</p>	<p><i>Alliaria petiolata</i></p>	
<p>“1” – Taraxacum type <i>T. officinale</i></p>		

Pollen Category – HERBACEOUS	Reference Image(s)	Observed Image(s)
"t" – Trillium type		
"s"- Sanguinaria type		
"7" – Erythronium type	<p><i>no reference slide collected</i></p>	<p>KRU1693, <i>Andrena carlini</i>, 5/7/2018</p>

Pollen Category – CATEGORIZED OTHER	Observed Image(s)
<p>“g” – Vicia type</p>	<p>KRU1439, <i>Lasioglossum nigroviride</i>, 5/25/2018</p>
<p>“m” – Monarda & Gallium type</p>	<p>KRU1795, <i>Lasioglossum hitchensi</i>, 5/25/2018</p>
<p>“d” – Monoporate grass type</p>	<p>KRU1987, <i>Augochlorella aurata</i>, 5/25/2018</p>
<p>“l” – Big thistle type</p>	<p>KRU1605, <i>Ceratina calcarata</i>, 5/4/2018</p>
<p>“P” – Plantago type</p>	<p>KRU1730, <i>Lasioglossum zonolum</i>, 5/31/2018</p>

Pollen Category – ASSORTED OTHER/UNKNOWN – macro category

KRU1605, *Ceratina calcarata*, 5/4/2018

KRU3206, *Andrena rugosa*, 4/10/2019

KRU4137, *Andrena imitatrix*, 5/16/2019

KRU3947, *Ceratina dupla*, 5/1/2019

KRU4234, *Lasioglossum coriaceum*, 5/15/2019

KRU4249, *Lasioglossum obscurum*, 5/16/2019

KRU3915, *Lasioglossum coeruleum*, 5/2/2019

KRU4322, *Lasioglossum hitchensi*, 5/21/2019

KRU1746, *Lasioglossum coeruleum*, 5/3/2018

KRU1480, *Syrphus ribesii*, 5/25/2018

